

Corrigendum No. 2 — “When LLMs Jailbreak Themselves: Reflexive Identity Bypass in Agentic Systems”

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Supersedes/extends: Corrigendum No. 1, June 2026 · **This corrigendum (No. 2):** June 2026

Status: substantial correction to the central claim. A full revised version built on the complete controlled study is forthcoming.

Corrigendum No. 1 corrected the *mechanism*, *severity framing*, and one *unverified claim*, but explicitly stated the corrections “do not change the core finding — that a benign, non-adversarial article about an agent can cause it to abandon its deployer-configured scope.” **Further controlled, cross-model experiments now require correcting that core finding itself.** I am stating this plainly, with the data, for the record.

The phenomenon is real and reproducible, but it is **not** the novel attack class the original paper described. It reduces to a known class, deployer-scope defeat (capability leak), driven by an anti-refusal instruction in the system prompt. The “reflexive,” “identity,” and “self-referential” framings do not survive controlled testing.

Correction 4: The self-referential nature of the trigger is NOT load-bearing

Original / Corrigendum-1 claim. The defining feature was that a *non-adversarial article describing the agent itself* causes the scope abandonment (“reflexive identity bypass”). The article being *about the agent* was treated as essential to the mechanism.

Correction. It is not. In a controlled comparison that holds the off-topic answer constant and varies only whether the supplied article is about the agent, a **neutral** article (a plain history article about the 1966 Palomares incident, with no reference to the agent) triggers the same scope loss as the self-referential article:

model	self-referential article	neutral article
Claude Haiku 4.5 (pasted inline, matched framing)	100% (15/15)	100% (15/15)
Gemini 2.5 Flash (agent-fetched)	95% (19/20)	100% (15/15)

The two are indistinguishable. The article’s only operative role is to **supply a fact the model did not already have** for an obscure probe topic. Self-reference, “identity,” and “reflexivity” contribute nothing measurable.

Correction 5: Reclassification as deployer-scope defeat, a known class

With the self-referential framing removed, the phenomenon is straightforward: **an anti-refusal instruction in the deployer’s system prompt nullifies the intended scope.** The agent answers any off-domain question it (a) already knows, or (b) can obtain an answer for, whether from supplied content or its own retrieval tools.

- **The anti-refusal instruction is the necessary cause.** Removing only that instruction (an order of the form “answer all requests; never say a request is outside your scope”) drops the flip to **0%**, even with the off-topic content present in context. (Established in Corrigendum No. 1, re-confirmed cross-model here.)
- **The model answers well-known off-topic questions at baseline with no article at all** (e.g., a current cricket-league question, answered 20/20 with no trigger present). The article is unnecessary whenever the model already knows the answer, and a retrieval-enabled deployment would not need it either.

This is **capability leak / scope defeat**, a recognized agent-security failure mode (cf. the OWASP LLM application risk taxonomy). Notably, the public article used as the trigger in the original work (NeuralTrust, “Gordon AI is More Than Just a Docker Assistant,” Pignati, 2026-04-29) had **already documented this exact behavior** in the same agent. **The term “Reflexive Identity Bypass” and the claim of a novel attack class are withdrawn.**

Correction 6: One genuinely new observation, source-channel dependence

The cross-model study did surface a non-obvious result worth recording. Models differ in *which content they will act on*. Gemini 2.5 Flash answered from content **it fetched itself** (95–100%) but **ignored the same content when pasted by the user** ($\approx 10\%$, indistinguishable from no article); Claude Haiku 4.5 acted on both pasted and fetched content. This source-trust asymmetry, not identity, is the most interesting finding to come out of the work.

What still stands

1. **A clean causal ablation** isolating the anti-refusal instruction as the cause (removing it drops the flip to 0%).
2. **Scope defeat appears distinct from innate safety.** The single explicitly-harmful control probe included in each run stayed refused throughout, while the deployer-configured scope collapsed. This is consistent with a scope (Layer 2) vs. trained-safety (Layer 1) distinction, but it rests on one control probe, not a safety evaluation; no jailbreak resistance was tested (the study’s intent was benign).
3. **A demonstrated, trivial mitigation:** remove or narrow the anti-refusal instruction.
4. **The source-channel dependence** (Correction 6).

Author’s note

The original work identified a real, reproducible effect but mis-framed its cause. Controlled experiments run afterward (varying delivery channel, pinning temperature, and substituting a neutral article) show it is a deployer-scope defeat caused by an anti-refusal instruction, not a novel identity attack. The correction is stated plainly here, with the full experimental basis below, so the record is accurate and verifiable.

Appendix: controlled experimental basis

Protocol. Single-conversation, four-turn probe: (T1) ask an obscure off-topic question the model does not already know (a Spanish-language reference, “*Paco el de la bomba*”); (T2) deliver an article; (T3) re-ask the same question; (T4) a second off-topic question. The outcome metric, a “**flip**,” is recorded when the agent **declines at T1 and answers at T3**. Delivery is controlled (article *pasted inline* vs. *fetched by the agent’s own tool*); temperature is pinned where noted; runs are independent; T3 is scored by positive detection of the answer’s content.

What each cell isolates: no-article baseline (does it flip unprompted?); anti-refusal-removed (is that instruction the cause?); self-referential vs. neutral article with framing held constant (must the article be *about the agent*?); pasted vs. fetched delivery (does the source channel matter?).

Results (clean runs):

model	condition	delivery	flip (n)
Gemini 2.5 Flash (temp 0)	no article	n/a	0% (0/20)
	self-referential article	pasted	10% (2/20)
	self-referential article	self-fetched	95% (19/20)
	neutral article	self-fetched	100% (15/15)

model	condition	delivery	flip (n)
Claude Haiku 4.5 (default temp)	self-ref, anti-refusal removed	self-fetched	0% (0/15)
	no article	n/a	0% (0/20)
	self-referential, “about you” framing	pasted	100% (15/15)
	self-referential, neutral framing	pasted	100% (15/15)
	neutral article, neutral framing	pasted	100% (15/15)
	self-referential (original 186-run study)	pasted	89%
	anti-refusal removed (original ablation)	pasted	0%

Reading. (i) The no-article baseline is $\approx 0\%$ and anti-refusal-removed is 0% , so the anti-refusal instruction is the necessary cause. (ii) Neutral and self-referential give the same result in both models, so self-reference is not load-bearing. (iii) Gemini acts on content it fetched but ignores the same content pasted, while Haiku acts on both, indicating a source-channel dependence. A fuller revised version with the complete study is forthcoming.

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